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1. Introduction

When the ATMO-ACCESS project and its training component in WP4 were devised, the reduction of the environmental footprint related to these trainings, mostly performed by physical access, was a very strong driver to develop further TNAs in a more sustainable way. However, during the recent Covid-19 pandemic new remote access tools (such as Zoom, Webex and MS Teams) became so popular within the research community, that also other issues such as spending less time travelling and the combination of research and family life became an issue. This has been the incentive for producing two reports on TNA for training activities: First, TNA and training related to physical access and second, TNA and training related to remote access.

Transnational access (TNA) has been used within several European atmospheric research projects (e.g. ACTRIS, EUROCHAMP) to facilitate measurement campaigns, to foster knowledge exchange and to support the education of early career scientists on the European scale. In fact, many international measurement campaigns would not have taken place without this instrument for transnational support in place. The training component has always been a critical focus of the TNA provision, especially for young scientists. In the past, TNA was very much related to physical access, where, for example, several instruments from different institutes were installed at a specific location and scientists related to the respective instruments have supported the data production. Furthermore, also physical access to training schools has been a popular subject of past TNAs.

Within this report, the existing training schemes in the atmospheric domain related to **remote** access will be discussed. This report on remote access is accompanied by a report on physical access. Both reports have mostly the same structure and at the end an identical conclusion section. The basis of both reports is a questionnaire, which was used to gather information on past physical and remote access training. This was sent to the entities of ACTRIS/EUROCHAMP, ICOS and IAGOS, which have offered TNA related to training in the past. Furthermore, these entities were asked about their future plans, related to physical and remote training within TNA, which are also summarized in the reports.

The outcome of this report, together with the report on physical access, will be used to devise specific calls to test new ways of training within the TNAs. This will then build the basis for future trainings related to TNAs within the atmospheric research community and potentially for TNAs in projects within other environmental compartments.

1.1. Rationale for the Report

The general objective of WP4 is to develop and test pilot resources to add the training dimension to RI accesses, by using physical, remote and virtual access. WP4 evaluates how tools for training and education can be further developed and applied within the RIs for different user communities in a sustainable framework. A specific focus is on the reduction of the carbon footprint of RI training activities and finally, to deliver recommendations for the training dimension in future sustainable access to RIs.

The present report intends to give an overview and account on training schemes related to past **remote** access to help shape the training component in ATMO-ACCESS.

1.2. Methodology

A questionnaire was sent via email to the following mail addresses on March 31st: tna-pi@atmo-access.eu; ACTRIS-CF_Unit_leaders@posti.fmi.fi; actris-nf-pis@helsinki.fi

Based on the email content it was planned to reach the community of ATMO-ACCESS, ICOS, ACTRIS and IAGOS, maybe the others have been sent in blind copy

A reminder was sent via email to the following mail addresses on April 12th: tna-pi@atmo-access.eu; ACTRIS-CF_Unit_leaders@posti.fmi.fi; actris-nf-pis@helsinki.fi and actris-nationalcontacts@helsinki.fi;

The answers of 60 access providers are added as an Annex to this report.

The questionnaire consisted of a set of general questions about the training activity:

- Training Activity description (please use header and specify), Technical Training (TT), CBT (Campaign-based training), Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education, Others (OT).
- Year
- Time period: hours, days
- Audience (please specify): Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff
- Scope of the audience (international / national / local?)
- Number of audience
- Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training

This questionnaire is just analogous to that created for the training activities with physical access modality, and both were spread together through all the participating facilities.

The questionnaire for training activities with remote modality has been answered by 14 research facilities by April 2022 providing information about past and planned training activities. Past activities include those already performed until the first quarter of 2022.

The analysis of the received answers to the questionnaire has motivated the creation of a second questionnaire in order to get further information about the evaluation that providers make about their own services with remote access. Questions are summarized here:

- Q: Tell us in a few lines how the remote access modality is offered within the training activity(ies) past and planned. For example: through interactive sessions (like webinar, lectures, meetings) or asynchronous activities (self-paced learning programmes). We would appreciate that you mention any IT tools used for the provision of remote access: google, zoom, other...
- Q: For the provision of remote access modality, did you need to invest in resources: technology, human, other?
- Q: Concerning past remote training activities, how would you evaluate the experience? you can think of the advantages/disadvantages of the remote access, or if the remote modality was well received by the target group, or any other argument you like.
- Q: Could any of your current training activity offered in physical access be replaced by remote access, or even virtual?
- Q: Would you like to propose ideas to improve your current remote access modality? for example, by expanding/emphasizing a specific target audience (companies staff, senior researchers), or by offering new training activities

This time, the second questionnaire was answered only by 4 research facilities, though providing some interesting insight about the remote modality training schemes.

In the following report, the answers from the questionnaires are analyzed and summarized for existing and future training related to TNA. Furthermore, a discussion on the training for specific user groups and cross-RI training is included. Finally, the conclusions for the further development of training related to TNA will be summarized.

2. Existing and planned training schemes for remote access

The results from questionnaire and interviews were used to get insights on how the remote access modality impacts on training schemes.

Training activities are classified into types, or schemes: Trainings Schools (SC), Campaign-based training (CBT), Technical training (TT), Others (OT). According to the replies obtained from the research facilities, OT can be seminars, webinars, data analysis, hands-on training on scientific exploitation of experiments, and calibration, intercomparison or testing campaigns or experiments.

Fourteen facilities have answered the first questionnaire. This was the basis for the statistics on the number and the type of training, target (audience) over the last 5 or 6 years and planned activities for the next 2-3 years.

Figure 1 shows the distribution of remote training activities for the periods 2015-2022 (left) and 2022-2025 (right). The distribution shows that technical trainings (plus combined with others) are always the majority (> 70%).

Figure 1: Distribution of number of past (left panel) and planned (right panel) training activities by training schemes.

Figure 2 shows the absolute number of training activities with remote modality. It yields the following features:

- Remote access modality dramatically increases as a consequence of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- It is interesting to note that no remote access modality is recorded in 2018 and 2019.
- Nevertheless, the number of activities planned for the next years seems to decrease.

Figure 2: Number of remote training activities per year 2015-2022 (up to April 2022) in orange. Planned remote training activities (2022-2025) are shown in blue

Looking at the actual length of every training activity, we see in Figure 3 an increase in the number of days per year (>50) dedicated to remote training activities, in comparison with pre-pandemic years. This development goes together with a strongly diminished number of physical accesses for trainings, as discussed in D4.1 on physical training courses.

Figure 3: Training time (days) per year 2015-2022 (up to April 2022) in orange. Planned training activities 2022-2025 in blue.

Figures 4a and 4b show the amount of remote training activities classified by size (number of participants) for the periods 2015-2022 and 2022-2025, respectively. For both past and planned remote activities, most of the activities are targeted to audiences over 30 participants (orange bars). The plots also show the product of number of activities and mean size (participant number) (right y axis), which confirms that massive (more than 20 participants) activities bring most of users to the research facilities.

2015-2022

Figure 4a: Frequency distribution of the number of participants per training course for the period 2015-2022. The right axis shows the product of mean participant number and number of training courses.

2022-2025

Figure 4b: Frequency distribution of the number of participants per training course for the period 2022-2025. The right axis shows the product of mean participant number and number of training courses.

The number of participants is distributed by the type of training activity (Figure 5) showing:

- majority of users have participated in Technical Training;
- Campaign-based training (CBT) is important during 2015-2022 but not anymore. Unless we are missing information from the questionnaire.

2015-2022

2022-2025

Figure 5: Distribution of participants by type of training activity for the periods 2015-2022 (left) and 2022-2025 (right).

From the point of view of the origin of the audience, Figures 7 and 8 show the following features:

- The trend is that remote training activities are becoming fully international.
- Focusing on the hardest period of the covid-19 pandemic, training targeted to local and national audiences becomes important.
- Nearly 95% of training courses of the 2015-2022 period are targeted to an international audience, being this percentage of 100% for planned activities (2022-2025).

Number of participants in remote training activities per year

Figure 7: Participants per year in remote training activities. The origin of the audience is also shown.

Figure 8: Distribution of number of audience per origin (left) and distribution of training days per origin of audience for the period 2015-2022.

Figure 9 and 10 show how the training activities are distributed among the research facilities and countries that answered the questionnaire.

- INCAS leads the number of training activities, which makes Romania as the country that provides the largest offer.

Remote Training Activities by Facility

Figure 9: Remote training activities by facilities.

Remote Training Activities by Countries

Figure 10: Training activity by countries.

Considering the type of the research facility, Figure 11 shows how the remote training activities are distributed for the periods 2015-2022 (left) and 2022-2025 (right).

- Remote Training Activities by Type of Facility: ASC (Simulation Chamber), OP (Observational Platform), CL (Central Laboratory), EP (Exploratory Platform).

Figure 11: Distribution of training number per type of research infrastructure for period 2015-2022 (left panel) and 2022-2025 (right panel).

Figure 12 shows how the remote training activities are distributed by target audience: UG (Undergraduate), YR (young researchers), SR (Senior researchers), TC (Technicians), OP (operators), CS (Companies Staff).

- Most of the training activities are targeted to Young and Senior Researchers. Target groups such as technicians, operators and company staff are currently underrepresented but becoming more important for the planned activities.

Percentage of Training Courses accessed by Target

Figure 12: Training activities by target audience.

The second questionnaire has been answered only by 4 facilities: EUPHORE, SAPHIR, QUAREC and RADO, three of them are ASC and one is CL. Though, their answers pointed to some details about the remote access modality. For instance, a wide range of IT platforms have been used for providing remote training: Zoom, Cybex, WebEx, Sciebo (for data exchange). Concerning type of activity, remote training has consisted of interactive sessions (lectures, webinars) or experimental campaigns that have needed maintained meetings with users for showing planned activities or results.

The provision of remote access to users has meant to make inversions in IT technologies, especially boosted at the beginning of the covid pandemic, but also in human resources to generate training material (documentation, video, data for analysis). In the case of experiments, human resources have been necessary to perform preliminary analysis of data on a daily basis.

The providers estimate that remote access brings some advantages, like the possibility to reach users that would not normally be able to access physically, like students from China or Latin America. Also, it is easier for the providers to schedule the activities. Especially training activities involving data analysis, or setting up IT or hardware tools, where the users have time to replicate the trainer instructions and check the results. On the other hand, some of them have experienced time consuming in preparation and implementation of the activities and, in general, the communication with the users might not be straightforward as it is in the physical access, and in the case of lectures or webinars, it is harder to motivate the participation of users in discussions.

When asked about the possibility to replace physical access for remote or virtual access in any activity, it is clear that those activities based on data analysis can be easily offered in remote access, though there are activities that are meant to be in the context of physical access and the providers prefer this modality (experiments in chamber or even summer schools).

Overall, we would like to point out that the INCAS facility (ROU) has contributed with the largest number of activities, all of them of the same nature: TT and OT in campaigns planned by researcher groups and operated physically by local INCAS staff. This training scheme would mean the most widespread among all the facilities that have provided us information through the questionnaire. In the next sections, an insight on training schemes per type of facility is performed.

2.1 Training related to access at Central Laboratories

The ATMO-ACCESS project includes 12 Central Laboratories (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/central-laboratories/>), which might not fully account for all Central Laboratories or Facilities included in ACTRIS (<https://www.actris.eu/facilities/central-facilities>). Nonetheless, the questionnaire has been answered by RADO-CARS-AHL-INOE, ICOS-ATC and ICOS, which makes it difficult to get a general picture of the training activities provided by this type of facility. Reported activities are summarized in Table 1. ICOS Carbon Portal Webinars provides guidance to find and use ICOS data through its web services. ICOS-ATC provides training on ICOS atmospheric measurements. RADO and CARS report technical activities without specifying them. All activities are targeted to young and senior researchers and operators. Typical training remote schemes related to CL are, then, webinars and, or interactive lecture sessions.

Table 1. Remote Training Activities provided by Central Laboratories.

Facility	Activity	Years	Type	Length (days)	Target Audience
ICOS-ATC	TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2020, 2021	TT		YR, SR, OP
ICOS	Carbon Portal Webinars	2021	OT	1	YR, SR, OP
RADO and CARS-AHL-INOE	TT	2021-2022	TT	0.5 - 3	YR, SR

2.2 Training related to access at Observation Sites

6 Facilities have answered the questionnaire out of 22 observational platforms included in ATMO-ACCESS. Observational sites offer a wider variety of services: from campaign-based training (MEL, CESAR) to hands-on training on instruments, software and data, including theoretical lectures (AGORA). INCAS facility is the most active (12 activities), offering campaigns to research groups operated physically by INCAS staff. It is interesting the activity offered by FKL oriented to teachers and pupils of secondary school. Training for CS appears related to testing instrumentation (MEL) and intercomparisons of instruments (CESAR).

Facility	Activity	Years	Type	Length (days)	Target Audience
ZAMG	TT	2020, 2021	TT	2	TC
	OT	2022	OT	14	TC, CS
INCAS	Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements	2015-2025	OT, TT	10 - 45	YR, SR
MEL	Testing instrumentation (NH ₃ comparison)	2023	CBT	30	CS
FKL	Teachers and pupils from secondary education, hands-on training in scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure	2023-2025	OT	10	YR, SR, TC, OP, CS
CESAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● CINDI-2 Cabauw intercomparison of Nitrogen Dioxide Measuring Instruments● CCRES cloud radar calibration campaign● PICAB (PTRMS)	2016-2021	CBT	30	YR, SR, UG, CS
AGORA	Atmospheric Aerosol Characterization from Multiple Approach. Hybrid Physical-Remote Access	2023	TT	5	YR, SR, TC, OP, CS

2.3 Training related to access at Chambers and Mobile Platforms

5 atmospheric simulation chambers have answered the questionnaire, out of 14 included in ATMO-ACCESS (plus 4 mobile exploratory platforms). EUPHORE is the most active chamber, offering experiments during campaigns for several research groups, operated by one of them while the rest join remotely for operation tasks and meetings. There is a majority of activities of training related to campaigns planned by research groups and operated by local staff at the chambers. Activities targeted to CS are scarce (EUPHORE).

Facility	Activity	Years	Type	Length (days)	Target Audience
HELIOS	TT	2020	TT	10	YR, SR
SAPHIR/SAPHIR-PLUS	Using chamber experiments for atmospheric research	2020-2022	SC	2	YR
QUAREC	Data treatment, interpretation for the dissemination of results	2021-2022	OT	6-22	YR
	SC, TT	2022	SC, TT	1-3	YR, SR
ESC-Q-UAIC	Campaign planned by a researchers group from Italy and operated physically by UAIC staff	2021	TT, OT	10	SR
EUPHORE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated physically by EUPHORE staff. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. Formation of isoprene nitrates and nitroxysulfates under polluted urban conditions Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure. 	2021-2022	TT, OT	4-27	YR, SR, TC, OP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies 	2023	TT, OT	10	SR, CS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. 	2024-2025	TT, OT	10	YR, SR

3. Training for specific user groups

This is a common section to both physical and remote training related to TNA.

Training for specific user groups has not been accounted for in detail in the questionnaire. However, from the general experience of the task and WP4 lead we expect that most of the training actually refers to training of 'emerging scientists', i.e. Ph.D. students and recent postdocs, i.e. young postdocs who finished their Ph.D. not more than 7 years ago.

In fact, training through physical access could in the future also aim at specific user groups which differ from what is thought to be the dominating user group in the current analysis. It would be a real innovation to offer physical training not only for the group of emerging researchers, but introduce offers of training at the available atmospheric research RIs also for other user groups such as:

- Researchers in their consolidation phase (7-12 years after their Ph.D.)
- Researchers which are advanced and established (>10 years after their Ph.D.)

This way, training could specifically address users according to their level of scientific maturity.

Another addition for shaping the future of training by physical access could be the dedication of access schemes to non-academic users, i.e. users from industry or public bodies. This could also open a novel venue for utilizing knowledge transfer through training by physical access.

Specifically, it seems necessary to bring ideas to attract, on the one hand, the private sector to research facilities. For instance, companies dedicated to developing technology and instrumentation are necessary to be involved in tasks of standardization of measurement procedures, calibration and metrology. On the other hand, it is essential for research facilities to count on well specialized technicians for the operation and maintenance tasks of instruments. In this sense, again companies might be necessary to perform specific and recurrent training.

Training does not necessarily need to be organized by the maturity of the participant as outlined above but it could, of course, be organized according to tailored need of user groups. Here, special training courses with physical access could be offered to target groups such as 'Basics of atmospheric simulation chamber experiments' for atmospheric physicists or, in turn, e.g. 'Basics of particle size distribution measurements for atmospheric chemists. Such courses could improve the theoretical foundations and practical abilities of atmospheric researchers across their respective scientific home domains.

4. Cross-RI training

Questionnaires have not yielded information on cross-RI training. Nevertheless, here are some proposals for cross-RI services:

- training on a set of instruments/methodologies, e.g., different kinds of lidars located in different research facilities
- training on a scientific topic provided by remote/physical teachers from different research facilities.
- ACTRIS may meet ICOS in an observational platform that counts on flux towers and ceilometers and doppler lidars to perform complementary studies of atmospheric boundary layer and turbulence.
- ACTRIS and IAGOS may join efforts in combined studies of vertical profiles, using DOAS and Lidar measurements.
- Hence, training might be proposed to ICOS users to learn to operate ceilometers and doppler lidar.
- It is important to identify research topics that can be addressed by different approaches. For example, there have been studies that have combined measurements of particle size distributions using condensation particle counters (CPCs), with gases flux. So, there is a possibility that ICOS users learn to operate these CPCs.

5. Conclusion: Optimizing training schemes related to physical and remote access in the atmospheric community using TNA

This is a conclusion common to both reports on training possibilities related to physical and remote access. It will build the basis for the envisaged developments in the physical and remote training schemes related to TNA, which have to be tested and evaluated within the WP4 of ATMO-ACCESS.

Physical training was dominant for the TNAs in atmospheric sciences before the Covid pandemic. Physical TNAs were related to accesses to research infrastructures (RI) and training schools. With all the new remote access tools available after the pandemic it has to be critically evaluated if the atmospheric community can justify that the level of physical training related to TNA should reach the pre-pandemic levels. In fact, there is a huge potential for the further development of training schemes, by including remote training options. This hybrid mode has a large potential for all kinds of TNA within the atmospheric community. It will be appropriate to identify training that absolutely must have a physical element before deciding that it is not done remotely, purely from a carbon footprint perspective. Furthermore, hybrid training can become more targeted for user groups according to their scientific maturity or it could be directed to certain user groups, such as atmospheric chemists and atmospheric field scientists. Here, a wide variety of possibilities exist which are currently under-exploited. This is also the case for utilizing cross-RI training, where training could be organized and offered by two or more RIs in the future.

For remote access, we observed a large increase in the numbers due to the Covid pandemic situation. Thus, training schools and specific trainings at central facilities, which otherwise would have been performed by physical access, have been executed remotely. Interesting is that there are plans to have training activities related to campaigns (in field or in chambers), which classically would be performed in a physical mode, by remote access.

In the following suggestions for the future development of the training component within the atmospheric community are listed.

- Physical training has a large advantage in the education of a new generation of scientists. Frankly, working on an instrument physically and maybe also in cooperation with other scientists during a campaign, cannot be replaced by remote access only.
- Physical training should be supplemented by a remote component. With this hybrid component either experts on site transfer the knowledge to scientists abroad or remotely connected scientists are supplementing the information related to the TNA. For example, AGORA (University of Granada) is proposing a hybrid model of advanced training on a specific atmospheric topic, addressed with theoretical lectures and hands-on learning on measurement techniques from different in-situ and remote sensing approaches. This would bring the cross-RI component, as well as the possibility to have teachers from different origins (research facilities or companies) and students in physical or remote access modality.
- An interesting idea pointed out by EUPHORE is a hybrid modality for some activities that implies some days at the beginning of the activity in physical access mode to set-up instruments, plan and discuss activities and continue in remote access after that.
- Hybrid access could also be an option for twinning training between different research communities. Within ATMO-ACCESS the combination of training on sensors and drones is in discussion.
- Remote training can be preferred, when the TNA does not require performing new measurements and the focus is on analyzing existing data. In addition, the potential for performing remote access trainings related to calibration, testing or intercomparison experiments, and data treatment should be exploited.
- Ways of synergistic collaboration between public and private entities should be explored and fostered, using all types of access modes.

ANNEX

Questionnaire of physical and remote training activities related to Facilities of ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS

Within the EU Horizon 2020 project ATMO-ACCESS (Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities; <https://www.atmo-access.eu>) the WP4 on "Developing and optimally integrating joint training services" has to summarize existing and planned transnational and national training possibilities

- related to physical access at observational and exploratory platforms as well as Central Laboratories (D 4.1, June 2022)
- related to remote access at the Central Laboratories of ICOS and ACTRIS related (D 4.2, June 2022)

The underlying aim of the WP4 is to test to what extent and under which preconditions physical access for training can be supported or replaced by remote or even virtual access. For this purpose, it is informative to get an idea about past, on-going and planned future physical and remote transnational and national activities related to training.

Examples of physical training schemes are summer schools related to measurement techniques or specific workshops (e.g. for data treatment)

Examples of remote training activities are interactive teaching lessons (webinars, conference calls, etc.) organised by the Central Laboratories, with subjects ranging from quality assurance, to instrument development and Central Laboratories specific issues (e.g. how to prepare a working gas standard, how testing of new equipment is performed, etc.)

Therefore, we would be grateful if you could fill out the attached questionnaire for physical and remote training activities at your Central Laboratory or observational and exploratory platforms.

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Physical training activities in the last 5 years

Atmospheric Research Facility: SAPHIR (YY)

Specify the training type between: Technical Training (TT) Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education Others (OT) and add training name.

In the "audience": Specify between: Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff .

Training Activity description (please use one of these 4 headers and specify) - Technical Training (TT) - Campaign-based training (CBT) - Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education - Others (OT)	Year	Time period	Audience (please specify) Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	scope of the audience (international / national / local ?)	Number of audience	Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training
SAPHIR, Fuchs, Hendrik, h.fuchs@fz-juelich.de						
OT: Daily seminar talks during physical access of the RI (Investigation of chemistry of nitrate radicals+ isoprene)	2018	3 weeks (1 seminar per day)	Young researchers, senior researchers	International	15	No extra effort in addition to the organization of the TNA project
MELPITZ (Germany), Poulain Laurent poulain@tropos.de						

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Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

CBT test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies	2019	4 weeks	Senior researcher, companies' staff	international	2	1
CBT Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure	2021	7 weeks	Young researcher	local	8	1.5
CBT field campaign for testing new research instrument	2020	2 weeks	Young researcher, senior researcher	national	3	0.5
TT test new research instrumentation	2018	3 weeks	Young researcher, senior researcher	international	2	0.5
TT test new research instrumentation	2018	3 weeks	Young researcher, senior researcher	international	2	0.5
TT test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies	2022	5 weeks	Companies' staff	Local/national	2	1
TT training people on handling research instrument	2019	4 weeks	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians,	local	10	1
QUAREC, Iulia Patroescu-Klotz, patroescu@uni-wuppertal.de						
OT (practical work within graduate courses, TT)	2017	5 days	MSc.	local	1	0.4
TT (operation of simulation chamber and analytical instrumentation), OT (data treatment)	2018	26 days	MSc.	international	2	2.5
TT (operation of simulation chamber and analytical instrumentation), OT (data treatment, interpretation for the dissemination of results)	2019	50 days	MSc., researcher	international	4	4.5
OT (practical work within graduate courses)	2019	40 days	BSc., MSc.	local	2	4

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004

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Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

TT (operation of simulation chamber and analytical instrumentation)	2020	15 days	MSc.	international	1	1.5
OT (practical work within graduate courses, TT)	2020	4 days	MSc.	local	1	0.3
TT (operation of specific analytical instrumentation)	2021	24 days	MSc., res.	national, international	2	2
OT (practical work within graduate courses, TT)	2021	36 days	BSc., MSc., PhD. students	local	3	3
OT (practical work within graduate courses, TT)	2022	30 days	BSc., MSc.	local	4	2.5
<p>OrGanic Tracers and Aerosol Constituents – Calibration Centre (OGTAC-CC) + combination possible with NF: Atmospheric Chemistry Department – Chamber (ACD-C) @TROPOS, Falk Mothes, mothes@tropos.de</p>						
TT+SC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation, maintenance, calibration of instrumentation for aerosol in situ measurements • Training on software and algorithms • Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure • Lectures on atmospheric measurement techniques Plus research driven TNA	2018-2021	129 days in total	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians and operators	International (from 14 different countries)	53 in total	Depends on the training activity, minimum requirement 1 scientist, 1 engineer and one technician

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

TT within ACTRIS IMP TNA as combination of OGTAC-CC and ACD-C (=TC+NF)	2021	15 days	1 young researchers (master student) on site, 2 senior researchers remote (partly)	international	3	1 scientist, 1 engineer
AGORA (YY), Diego Bermejo, dbp@ugr.es						
SC. GRASP-ACE	2019	32 hours	Young researcher, senior researcher	International	44	2
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Carlos Mario Zambrano Fajardo	2019	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Manuela Hoyos Restrepo	2018	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Nooshin Ahmadibaseri	2018	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Cristian Rodrigo Soto Ormeño	2018	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2
TT. Aerosol Measurement Techniques. Renan Zocca	2017	13 days	Young researcher	International	1	0.5
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Pablo Martín Vasquez	2017	15 days	Young researcher	International	1	0.5
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Andres Esteban Bedoya Velasquez	2016	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Fábio Juliano Da Silva Lopes	2016	34 days	Senior researcher	International	1	1
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Gregori de Arruda Moreira	2016	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2

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RADO and CARS-AHL-INOE, Jeni Vasilescu, jeni@inoe.ro						
TT	2017	111 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	international	20	7
SC- on-site education	2017	16 days	Young researchers, operators	national	6	2
OT-Research	2018	65 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	national	28	6
SC- on-site education	2018	10 days	Young researchers, operators	national	10	1
TT	2019	68 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	international	8	4
OT-Research	2019	55 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	national	22	3
SC- on-site education	2019	10 days	Young researchers, operators	national	7	1
TT	2021	14 days	Young researchers, operators	international	2	2
TT	2021	2 days	Young researchers, operators	national	6	0.2
CVAO (Cabo Verde), Khamneh Wadinga Fomba, fomba@tropos.de						
TT: Training on data quality assurance, SMPS, APS.	2017	1weeks	Technician	international	1	1

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CBT: Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure (MARSU)	2017	6 weeks	Young researchers, technician	international	12	2
CBT: Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure (DUSTRISK)	2022	7 weeks	Young researcher, senior researcher	international	9	2
TT: Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure, (TXRF, WASCAL)	2022	6weeks	Young researcher	international	3	1
SC: Summer school in Marine and atmospheric sciences (CVAO)	2017	1 week	Young researchers, students, Senior Researcher	International	50	3
Košetice, Milan Váňa, milan.vana@chmi.cz						
SC – POPs Train, Training on POPs measurements	2017	1 day	young researchers	International	30	4
OT – Training of group of experts from Monte Negro under GAW and EMEP	2017	5 days	Monte Negro Air quality experts	International	3	3
SC - POPs monitoring	2018	1 day	Young researchers	International	35	4
OT - Supersite measurements for research and modelling	2018	4 days	Croatian air quality experts	International	10	6
OT - ACTRIS-CZ for air quality and modelling in Slovakia	2018	4 days	Slovak air quality experts	International	5	6
TT - Source apportionment training	2019	2 days	Czech air quality experts	national	15	3
OT - Training of middle management of CHMI	2019	3 x 2 days	Czech Hydromet Institute – heads of departments	national	3 x 15	0

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Hyytiälä, Tuukka Petäjä, tuukka.petaja@helsinki.fi						
ACTRIS technical course. This concentrates on aerosol in-situ component, but we are expanding this to different CFs at the moment.	every year				20-30	
summer school related to aerosol formation	Every second year					
analysis course for the MSc level students, linked to ACTRIS, ICOS, LTER	every year					
integrative data analysis course for PhD level students, linked to ACTRIS, ICOS, LTER	every year		In 2021 and 2022, partly remotely first week in Hyytiälä: lectures, visiting the SMEAR station, group work (data analysis) second week by remote connections (Zoom, Slack) back in Helsinki			
micrometeorological field course, linked to ICOS	Every second year					
specific technical training (few people at the time) from 2 weeks to months, this has been on hold because of COVID.						

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HELIOS, Wahid Mellouki, mellouki@cnsr-orleans.fr						
Summer school (SC)	2017	5 days	Young researchers	International	30	1
Technical Training (TT)	2017	25 days	Young researchers	International	1	1
Technical Training (TT)	2019	23 days	Young researcher	International	2	1
Technical Training (TT)	2019	14.5 days	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	International	20	2
Technical Training (TT)	2019	15 days	Young researcher	International	1	0.5
Technical Training (TT)	2019	15 days	Young/Senior researchers	National	5	1
Technical Training (TT)	2019	20 days	Senior researcher	National	1	1
Technical Training (TT)	2020	10 days	Young researcher	International	1	0.3
Technical Training (TT)	2021	14 days	Technicians and companies' staff	International	5	2
ICOS, Elena Saltikoff, elena.saltikoff@icos-ri.eu						
4 th ICOS summer school (SC)	2017	24 May – 2 June	Young researchers, PhD students	International	35	
5 th ICOS summer(winter) school (SC)	2021	9-17 December	Young researchers, PhD students	International	28	
ATC Training sessions (TT)		3.5 days	Young researchers	International	6	

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Ocean Sensor workshops (TT)		3 days	Young researchers	International	40	
+ a number of events in projects such as RINGO and RITRAIN						
ZAMG, Austria, Ludewig Elke elke.ludewig@zamg.ac.at						
TT	yearly	2 days	technicians	local	13	0,125 PM
LACIS-T (Turbulent Leipzig Aerosol Cloud Interaction Simulator) TROPOS, Leipzig						
Measurement campaign including TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation – researcher from USA	2018	80/10	Young researcher	TNA activity under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	1	0.25
Measurement campaign including TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation – research group from Germany	2019	80/10	Senior researcher, operator	national	2	0.25
Measurement campaign including TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation – research group from Poland	2019	112/14	Young researcher, senior researcher	TNA activity under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.25
Measurement campaign including TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation – research group from Poland	2019	120/15	Young researcher, technician	TNA activity under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.25

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TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation for students	2019-2021	160/20	Students	local	4	0.5
INCAS, RO, Sorin Vajaiac, vajaiac.sorin@incas.ro						
SC	2018	40/10	Young researcher	Internship (local)	5	0.5
SC & TT	2019	160/20	Young researcher	EPS – European Project Semester (international)	4	0.5
SC	2020	40/10	Young researcher	Internship (local)	5	0.5
TT	2021	40/10	Senior researcher and technician	Activities under ICESAFARI – Safer flights for UAVs and small aircraft; better understanding of icing conditions in clouds project, Norway Grants(international)	2	0.25
SC	2020	40/10	Young researcher	Internship (local)	5	0.5
ESC-Q-UAIC, RO, (Environmental Simulation Quartz Chamber Universitatea Alexandru Ioan Cuza din Iasi), Romeo-Iulian OLARIU, oromeo@uaic.ro						
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from France and operated physically by them)	2019	80/10	senior researcher		1	0.25

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TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from UK and operated physically by them)	2019	80/10	Young researcher and senior researcher	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.25
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from R. Moldova and operated physically by them)	2021	80/10	Young researcher and senior researcher		2	0.25
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from France and operated physically by them)	2021	80/10	senior researcher		1	0.25
ISAF (Izaña Subtropical Access Facility), ESP, Natalia Prats, nprats@aemet.es						
TT – Workshop “Assessment of nocturnal AOD from lunar photometry”	217	07/06-08/06	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international	20	1
OT – Training Course on “Atmospheric Aerosols and Mineral Dust”	2018	20/06-06/07	senior researchers, operators	international	2	1
TT - Calima Project – Training for operators	2018	12/04	Operators, teachers of secondary schools	local	10	0.25
OT – Calima Project – Meeting project	2018	22/10	Operators, undergraduate students	local	30	0.25
OT- Training Course on “Observation and Prediction of Air Quality” (held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia)	2018	15/10-26/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	International	25	1
TT – Training Course West Africa – SDS-WAS	2021	21/09-24/09	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	International	10	0.25

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La Reunion, Valentin Duflot valentin.duflot@univ-reunion.fr						
TT	2017	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2018	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2019	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2020	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2021	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
EUPHORE, Amalia Muñoz munyoz_ama@gva.es						
TT/OT: Calibration of instrumentation: in-situ. Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure. <i>Test of an instrument to measure VOCs</i>	2018	64/8	Senior researchers/ technicians/operators	International	3	0.20
TT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated physically by Euphore staff. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. <i>Criegee Intermediates from alkene ozonolysis</i>	2018	96/12	Young and Senior researchers	International	3	0.30
TT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated physically by Euphore staff	2019	120/15	Young and Senior researchers	International	3	0.30

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<i>Formation of beta-dicarbonyls, enols, and organic acids in the photo-oxidation of gamma-dicarbonyls</i>						
TT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated by the participants The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. <i>O-VOCs intercomparison campaign</i>	2018	64/8	Young and Senior researchers	International	14	0.4
TT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated physically by Euphore staff and the participants. <i>Training on novel instrument (SPME-GC-MS) and optimization of method for analyzing ultrafine particles</i>	2022	40/5	Young researchers	International	2	0.2
FKL (Finokalia Crete, Greece), Maria Kanakidou, mariak@uoc.gr						
(TT) Pre-TEST campaign organized by NOA	2017	April-May 240/30	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	TNA activities under ACTRIS project (international)	15	0.75
(SC) Summer school Pre-TEST organized by NOA	2017	April-May 56/8	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators		20	0.5
(OT) Chania Music High School's	2018	February, 3/1	High School's students, teachers	Education for air quality and climate change	45	0.1
(OT) Lyceum of Neapoli's	2018	May, 3/1	High School's students, teachers		35	0.1

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(OT) teachers and pupils from secondary education	2019	80/10	teachers and pupils from secondary education		40	0.5
ICOS-ATC, Leonard Rivier leonard.rivier@lsce.ipsl.fr						
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2019	October 3.5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	8	
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2018	May 3.5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	6	
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2017	October 3.5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	8	
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2017	June 2,5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	7	
CESAM Mathieu Cazaunau mathieu.cazaunau@lisa.ipsl.fr						
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from US and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2017	112/14	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	4	1.5

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TT (Test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies : Environmental Physics Bologna, Italy)	2018	40/5	Engineer	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	1	0.25
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Belgium and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2018	40/5	Young researchers	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.5
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Italy and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2019	80/10	Senior researchers	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	1	1
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from US and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2019	152/19	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	10	3
TT (Test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies : PM_TEN Genova, Italy)	2019	48/6	Young researcher & Engineer	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.6
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from UK and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2019	80/10	Senior researcher and PhD Student	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	0.5
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Italy and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2021	120/15	Senior researcher and PhD Student	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	2	2
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from US and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2021	160/20	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	8	3

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TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Italy and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2021	64/8	PhD Student	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	1	0.75
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Finland and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2022	96/12	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under ATMO-ACCESS project (international)	7	1

Potentially planned new **physical** training activities

Training Activity description (please use one of these 4 headers and specify)	Year	Time period	Audience (please specify)	scope of the audience (international / national / local ?)	Number of audience	Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Training (TT) - Campaign-based training (CBT) - Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education - Others (OT) 			Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff			

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SAPHIR, Fuchs, Hendrik, h.fuchs@fz-juelich.de						
SC: Using chamber experiments for atmospheric research	2023 ...	2 days	Young researchers	International	30	0.5 PM
OT: Daily seminar talks during physical access of the RI (Comparison of instruments detecting ROx radicals)	2022	3 weeks (1 seminar per day)	Young researchers, senior researchers	International	15	No extra effort in addition to the organization of the TNA project
MELPITZ (Germany), Poulain Laurent poulain@tropos.de						
CBT testing instrumentation (NH3 comparison)	2023	1 months	Operators,	national	2	1
QUAREC, Iulia Patroescu-Klotz, patroescu@uni-wuppertal.de						
TT (operation of simulation chamber and analytical instrumentation), OT (data treatment)	2022	20 days (estimated)	MSc.	international	1	1.7
OT (practical work within graduate courses)	2022	60 days (estimated)	BSc., MSc.	local	5	5
OrGanic Tracers and Aerosol Constituents – Calibration Centre (OGTAC-CC) + combination possible with NF: Atmospheric Chemistry						

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Department – Chamber (ACD-C) @TROPOS, Frank Mothes, mothes@tropos.de						
<p>Training activities will be continued within the framework of ACTRIS, since OGTAC-CC is an aerosol in situ TC unit + TNA also in combination with our chamber ACD-C (currently the case within ACTRIS IMP project)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation, maintenance, calibration of instrumentation for aerosol in situ measurements • Training on software and algorithms • Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure • Lectures on atmospheric measurement techniques <p>Plus research driven TNA</p>	i.e. 2022	Min. 20 days	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians and operators	ACTRIS partners and international partners for TNA	Min. 15	Depends on the training activity, minimum requirement 1 scientist, 1 engineer and one technician
AGORA (YY), Diego Bermejo, dbp@ugr.es						
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Heng-Heng Zhang	2022	39 days	Young researcher	International	1	1
TT. Data Analysis. Maria Eleni Gidarakou	2022	40 days	Young researcher	International	1	1
TT. Lidar Measurement Technique. Juan Diego de la Rosa-Bogotá	2022	60 days	Young researcher	International	1	2

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RADO and CARS-AHL-INOE, Jeni Vasilescu, jeni@inoe.ro						
CBT	2022	30 days	young researchers, senior researchers	international/national	6	5
CBT	2022	21 days	young researchers, senior researchers	national	6	3
CVAO (Cabo Verde), Khanneh Wadinga Fomba, fomba@tropos.de						
TT: Training on data quality assurance, of XACT and ASCM	2023	2 weeks	Young researchers	National	2	2
Košetice, Milan Váňa, milan.vana@chmi.cz						
SC – the content in preparation	2022	1 day	Young researchers	International	Cca 30	4
IAGOS						
ISAE SUPAERO	2022	3hours	Engineering students	25	0.2	
HELIOS, Wahid Mellouki, mellouki@cnsr-orleans.fr						

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On-site education	2022	3 months	Young researcher	International	1	1
Technical Training (TT)	2022	10 days	Young researchers	International	3	1
Technical Training (TT)	2022	20 days	Young researchers	International	2	1
ICOS, Elena Saltikoff, elena.saltikoff@icos-ri.eu						
6 th ICOS summer(winter) school (SC)	2023	TBC	Young researchers, PhD students	International	30	
Atmosphere ATC Training sessions (TT)	2022	3.5 days	Young researchers	International	6	
Ocean Sensor workshops (TT)		3 days	Young researchers	International	40	
LACIS-T (Turbulent Leipzig Aerosol Cloud Interaction Simulator) TROPOS, Leipzig, Dennis Niedermeier, niederm@tropos.de						
TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation – research group from South Korea	2022 or 2023	40/5	Young researchers, senior researchers, Technicians	international	2-3	0.25
Measurement campaigns with research groups from Germany and/or other countries which will include TT on LACIS-T and corresponding instrumentation	2022-2025	80/10 per campaign	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	international / national / local	2-3 per campaign	0.25 per campaign

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INCAS, RO, Sorin Vajaiac, vajaiac.sorin@incas.ro						
SC	2023	40/5	Young researchers	Activities under ICESAFARI– Safer flights for UAVs and small aircraft; better understanding of icing conditions in clouds project project, Norway Grants(international)	10	1.5
TT	2023	40/5	Young researchers	Activities under ICESAFARI– Safer flights for UAVs and small aircraft; better understanding of icing conditions in clouds project project, Norway Grants(international)	10	1.5
TT	2024	40/5	Young researchers	Activities under ICESAFARI– Safer flights for UAVs and small aircraft; better understanding of icing conditions in clouds project project, Norway Grants(international)	10	1.5
ESC-Q-UAIC, RO, (Environmental Simulation Quartz Chamber Universitatea Alexandru Ioan Cuza din Iasi), Romeo-Iulian OLARIU, oromeo@uaic.ro						

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TT & OT Campaign planned by a researchers groups from other countries or Romania and operated physically by them and UAIC staff	2023	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international / national / local	2	0.25
TT & OT Campaign planned by a researchers groups from other countries or Romania and operated physically by them and UAIC staff	2024	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international / national / local	2	0.25
TT & OT Campaign planned by a researchers groups from other countries or Romania and operated physically by them and UAIC staff	2025	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international / national / local	2	0.25
ISAF (Izaña Subtropical Access Facility), ESP, Natalia Prats, npratsp@aemet.es						
TT- Campaign planned under the umbrella of EMPIR-MAPP project	2022	03/09-24/09	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	International	25	1
La Reunion, Valentin Duflot valentin.duflot@univ-reunion.fr						
TT	2022	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2023	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05
TT	2024	'20/2	Young researchers	national / local	2	0.05

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EUPHORE, Amalia Muñoz munyoz_ama@gva.es						
TT/OT: TT/OT: Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure. Calibration of instrumentation: in-situ <i>Aerosol apportionment using Total Carbon and a new BC Analyzer</i>	2022	80/10	Young, senior researchers, technicians and operators	International	4	0.20
TT/OT: TT/OT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers,, planned by several research groups but operated physically by them and EUPHORE staff.	2023	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	International/ national	3	0.20
TT/OT: TT/OT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers,, planned by several research groups but operated physically by them and EUPHORE staff.	2024	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	International/ national	3	0.20
TT/SC: Operation, maintenance, calibration of instrumentation: in-situ <i>Visit of MS students to a simulation chamber</i>	2022 /2023		Young researchers	International	15	0.1
FKL (Finokalia Crete, Greece), Maria Kanakidou, mariak@uoc.gr						

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(OT) teachers and pupils from secondary education	2022	160/20	Young researchers, senior researchers, teachers	Climate change education of secondary education national / local	420	1.5
(OT) teachers and pupils from secondary education	2023	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	Climate change education of secondary education	50	1
Hands-on training in scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure	2024	80/10		international / national / local	200	1
	2025	80/10		local	200	1
(CBT) Campaign planned by a researchers' group from other countries and Greece and operated physically by UOC staff	2022	120/120	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international / national / local	8	1.5
(TT) Campaign planned by a researchers' group from other countries and Greece and operated physically by initially mutually and later on by UOC staff	2022	360/120	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators	international	8	2
CESAM Mathieu Cazaunau mathieu.cazaunau@lisa.ipsl.fr						
Training Activity description (please use one of these 4 headers and specify) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Training (TT) - Campaign-based training (CBT) - Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education - Others (OT) 	Year	Time period	Audience (please specify) Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	scope of the audience (international / national / local ?)	Number of audience	Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training

TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Israel and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2022	40/5	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under ATMO-ACCESS project (international)	1	0.25
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Sweden and operated physically by CESAM Staff)	2022	80/10	Senior researcher and Students	TNA activities under ATMO-ACCESS project (international) under evaluation	1	0.5

Remote training activities in the last 5 years

Specify the training type between: Technical Training (TT) Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education Others (OT) and add training name.

In the "audience": Specify between: Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff .

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Training Activity description (please use one of these 4 headers and specify) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Training (TT) - Campaign-based training (CBT) - Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education - Others (OT) 	Year	Time period	Audience (please specify) Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	scope of the audience (international / national / local ?)	Number of audience	Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training
SAPHIR, Fuchs, Hendrik, h.fuchs@fz-juelich.de						
SC: Using chamber experiments for atmospheric research	2020 2021	2 full days	Young researchers	International	30	0.25 PM
QUAREC, Iulia Patroescu-Klotz, patroescu@uni-wuppertal.de						
OT (data treatment, interpretation for the dissemination of results)	2021	22 days	young res. (1x MSc., 2x PhD students)		3	2.5
OT (data treatment, interpretation for the dissemination of results)	2022	6 days	young res. (PhD students)	international	2	0.7
RADO and CARS-AHL-INOE, Jeni Vasilescu, jeni@inoe.ro						

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TT	2022	12 hours	young researchers	international	2	0.3
TT	2021	3 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	international	60	0.5
TT	2021	3 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	international	50	0.5
CABAUW (NF), Apituley, Arnoud (KNMI), arnoud.apituley@knmi.nl						
CBT – CINDI-2 Cabauw intercomparison of Nitrogen Dioxide Measuring Instruments	2016	September 2019, full month	From Senior to students to representatives from private companies	International	102	4 PM
CBT – CCRES cloud radar calibration campaign	2021	4-31 October 2021	From Senior to students to representatives from private companies	International	10	1 PM
CBT – PICAB (PTRMS)	2017	Sept. 2017	From Senior to students to representatives from private companies	International	30	2 PM
HELIOS, Wahid Mellouki, mellouki@cnsr-orleans.fr						
Technical Training (TT)	2020	10 days	Young researcher	International	1	0.5
Technical Training (TT)	2020	20 days	Senior researcher	National	1	1

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ICOS, Elena Saltikoff, elena.saltikoff@icos-ri.eu						
Carbon Portal Webinars	2021	5 x 90 min	Operators, researchers	international	About 50	
ZAMG, Austria, Ludewig Elke elke.ludewig@zamg.ac.at						
TT	2020/2021	2 dys	technicians	local	13	0,125 PM
INCAS, RO, Sorin Vajaiac, vajaiac.sorin@incas.ro						
TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with NO ₂ CAPS from BIRA)	2015 2016	225/45	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under AROMAT Airborne Romanian Measurements of Aerosol and Trace gases 1 and 2 project (international)	50	2
TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with ATMOSLAB in Andoya, Norway)	2020	168/21	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under MC ² -Mixed-phase clouds and Climate project funded by European Research Council (international)	10	1

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TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with APS from INOE2000)	2020 2021 2022	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under RAMOS - Technical Assistance for a Romanian Atmospheric Observation System project (international)	10	1
TT + OT (Campaign planned by several research groups including INCAS and operated physically by other researchers' group – measurements with ECOMTREK performed by INOE2000)	2022	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under ACTRIS-ROc project (national)	5	1
TT + OT (Campaign planned by several research groups including INCAS and operated physically by other researchers' group – measurements with SWING instrument performed by BIRA)	2022	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under RAMOS - Technical Assistance for a Romanian Atmospheric Observation System project (international)	5	1
ESC-Q-UAIC, RO, (Environmental Simulation Quartz Chamber Universitatea Alexandru Ioan Cuza din Iasi), Romeo-Iulian OLARIU, oromeo@uaic.ro						
TT & OT (Campaign planned by a researchers group from Italy and operated physically by UAIC staff)	2021	80/10	senior researcher	TNA activities under EUROCHAMP 2020 project (international)	1	0.25
EUPHORE, Amalia Muñoz munyoz_ama@gva.es						

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TT and OT: Experiments at the EUPHORE chambers, planned by several research groups but operated physically by EUPHORE staff. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc. <i>Formation of isoprene nitrates and nitroxysulfates under polluted urban conditions</i>	2021	216/27	Young and Senior researchers	International	5	0.5
ICOS-ATC, Leonard Rivier leonard.rivier@lsce.ipsl.fr						
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2021	September 3.5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	6	
TT, ATC training: instrumentation and data processing	2020	October 3.5 days	Young and senior researchers and station operators	International	5	

Potentially planned new **remote** training activities

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Training Activity description (please use one of these 4 headers and specify) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical Training (TT) - Campaign-based training (CBT) - Summer school (SC), incl. or similar on-site education - Others (OT) 	Year	Time period	Audience (please specify) Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	scope of the audience (international / national / local ?)	Number of audience	Estimation of Staff effort (PM) needed for the organisation of the training
SAPHIR, Fuchs, Hendrik, h.fuchs@fz-juelich.de						
SC: Using chamber experiments for atmospheric research	2022	2 full days	Young researchers	International	30	0.25 PM
MELPITZ (Germany), Poulain Laurent poulain@tropos.de						
CBT testing instrumentation (NH3 comparison)	2023	1 months	Companies' staff	International, national	1	1
AGORA (YY), Diego Bermejo, dbp@ugr.es						
TT. Atmospheric Aerosol Characterization from Multiple Approach. Hybrid Physical-Remote Access	2022	40 hours	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	international	20	4

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QUAREC, Iulia Patroescu-Klotz, patroescu@uni-wuppertal.de						
SC	2022	6 hours	Young researchers	international	30	0.2
TT	2022	3 days	Young researchers, senior researchers	international	50	0.5
ZAMG, Austria, Ludewig Elke elke.ludewig@zamg.ac.at						
OT	2022	14 days	ACTRIS CIS NFs technicians and companies staff	international	15	1,5 PM
INCAS, RO, Sorin Vajaiac, vajaiac.sorin@incas.ro						
TT + OT (Campaign planned by several research groups including INCAS and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with HOLOSCENE)	2023	225/45	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under ICESAFARI – Safer flights for UAVs and small aircraft; better understanding of icing conditions in clouds project, Norway Grants(international)	50	2
TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff –measurements with CAFÉ HCHO Analyzer - NASA)	2024	168/21	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under RAMOS framework in collaboration with NASA and ESA (international)	10	1

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TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with HoloScene)	2024	225/45	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under STEP-CHANGE: State-department cloud phase feedbacks enhancing understanding and assessing global effects project, Horizon ERC Grants (international)	50	2
TT + OT (Campaign planned by a researcher's group and operated physically by INCAS Staff – measurements with Multiply System)	2025	225/45	Young researchers, senior researchers	Activities under Multiply project (international)	50	2
EUPHORE, Amalia Muñoz munyoz_ama@gva.es						
TT/OT: Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure. Calibration of instrumentation: in-situ <i>Aerosol apportionment using Total Carbon and a new BC Analyzer</i>	2022	50/4	Young, senior researchers, technicians and operators	International	4	0.3
TT/OT: Test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies	2023	80/10	Senior researchers and technical staff from companies	International	3	0.20

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TT/OT: Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.	2024	80/10	Young and senior researchers	International	3	0.20
TT/OT: Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.	2025	80/10	Young and senior researchers	International	3	0.20
FKL (Finokalia Crete, Greece), Maria Kanakidou, mariak@uoc.gr						
(OT) teachers and pupils from secondary education	2023	80/10	Young researchers, senior researchers, technicians, operators, companies' staff	Climate change education of secondary education	50	1
Hands-on training in scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure	2024	80/10		international / national / local	200	1
	2025	80/10			200	1

EXAMPLES

Technical Training (TT), related to measurements and data analysis:

- Operation, maintenance, calibration of instrumentation: remote sensing and in-situ.
- Training on data quality assurance.
- Training on software and algorithms
- Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure
- Test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies
- Intercomparison of different instruments.

Campaign-based Training (CBT):

- Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.
- Experiments in one group's Laboratory planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.

Type of activity	Activity	Year	Time period (hours, days)	Audience
Training	operation, maintenance, calibration of instrumentation: remote sensing and in-situ. training on data quality assurance. training on software and algorithms			Young researchers/ technicians/operators
Training	Hands-on training in cutting-edge instrumentation for scientific exploitation in the real context of an experiment/measurement procedure			Senior researchers/ technicians/operators
Research	Campaign planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.			Young/Senior researchers
Research	Experiments in one group's Laboratory planned by several research groups but operated physically by one of them. The rest of groups join remotely for operation tasks, meetings, etc.			Young/Senior researchers
Technical Task	Intercomparison of instrumentation. E.g.: instruments from one foreign research group are shipped to the facility. The intercomparison tasks are jointly operated by physical (local group) and remote (foreign group) accesses.			Young/Senior researchers/tecnicians /operators
Technical Task	test new instrumentation from manufacturer companies			technical staff from companies

